

Business Development Strategy in Pt. Revolver Love Coffee, Badung Regency, Bali: Based On Swot Analysis

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Abstract: The development of the community's economy is marked by businesses selling various snacks and drinks. The type of business that is starting to develop on the island of Bali is "Coffee Shop" one of the names of businesses engaged in this type of business is PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi has now opened locations in several points in the Kuta area, namely Seminyak, Petitenget and Canggu. The purpose of the study was to determine the external and internal factors in researching and reviewing the strategies used by PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi for business development used the EFE, IFE, and SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threats) analysis approaches. The data analysis method used qualitative methods, the data collection techniques used interviews, the type of data used as primary data, and the sampling technique used was random sampling. The results show that the EFE PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi's approach can take advantage of opportunities and avoid threats; the results of the IFE approach show that PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi has a relatively good internal condition or ability to take advantage of its strengths and can overcome its weaknesses. The results of the SWOT analysis are in prime and stable condition, so it is possible to continue expanding and supporting an aggressive growth policy (Growth-oriented strategy). Moreover, strategies can be applied by PT. Cinta Kopi's revolvers for business development are product development strategy, quality control, and marketing intelligence.

Keywords: SWOT Analysis, Business Strategy, Business Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Economic development in Indonesia is currently experiencing a decline due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which is happening not only in Indonesia but worldwide [21]. Many layoffs (Termination of Employment) from every company, especially in the tourism sector, significantly impact Bali's province. The Food and Beverage Industry is the sub-sector of choice for people, especially those affected by the Covid-19 pandemic situation because food and beverages are needs that are always needed by the community [31]. It is not only a necessity but also part of a lifestyle, especially in this pandemic era which results in more learning or office activities being carried out online or work from home (WFH), which requires supporting facilities such as wifi and strategic places, so that this can increase people's intention to do so in restaurants or cafes [20].

Food and beverage industry players are also optimistic that this industry will soon accelerate with the improvement in community conditions [22]. Food or drink is not one of the main factors, but there are other factors. Increasingly fierce competition, especially in the food and beverage industry, can influence consumer behaviour to be more selective in choosing a restaurant or café [1] [16]. Another factor that is intended is the atmosphere of a restaurant or cafe that includes friendly employee service to customers, attractive room designs, delicious and varied food and beverage products

and positive experiences that stick in the minds of consumers while in the restaurant or café [5] [27] [15] [26] [23]. With the significant growth of the culinary business, especially coffee shops in Bali, there will be competition between coffee shop owners, which will affect profits. To prevent this, coffee shop owners must have an excellent strategy to deal with their competitors.

PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi or Revolver Espresso is a unique coffee shop in Bali in the Seminyak area, the first store. The main menu that characterises Revolver is, of course, the coffee drink that coffee lovers say to be one of the best coffees in Bali. Revolver sells not only drinks but also food as a support for the menu as well as merchandise in the form of coffee grounds, clothing and accessories with Revolver designs. The shop's unique atmosphere can invite people's curiosity to visit the coffee shop [8]. Until now, Revolver has three store locations, namely Seminyak, Petitenget and Canggu. When viewed from the competition in the coffee shop and its surroundings, many new coffee shops are present, causing increasingly fierce competition. The existence of this competition makes Revolver Espresso need to prepare a strategy and implement it in order to survive and increase sales. With a good taste of coffee, uniqueness of the place, complete facilities and excellent service, it can make Revolver Espresso a comfortable coffee shop and in demand by the public, especially tourists.

During the Covid-19 pandemic era, it is undeniable that Revolver Espresso also experienced an impact which caused a decrease in sales and the employee work system experienced a reduction in working days. However, during the Covid-19 pandemic, Revolver Espresso was able to open a new branch with a broader area, namely Revolver Canggu, which began operating at the end of 2020. Previous Research by [1] stated that a company could develop strategies to overcome external threats and seize existing opportunities. It is carried out by analysing, formulating, and evaluating these strategies, commonly called strategic planning [18] [32]. The primary purpose of strategic planning is to objectively see the internal and external conditions so the company can anticipate the external environment. In this case, the functions of management, consumers, distributors, and competitors can be distinguished. Strategic planning is essential to gaining a competitive advantage [16]. Based on the background described, this study aims to analyse and explain the Business Development Strategy at PT. Coffee Love Revolver.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Business strategy

A business strategy is a comprehensive, integrated and unified plan which guides the activities carried out to achieve a company's goals [2]. In other words, business strategy is a set of goals and objectives, policies and rules that give direction to the company's efforts from time to time, at each level and its references and allocations, especially as the company's response to the environment and competitive conditions that are constantly changing. Changed [29]. Business strategy is essential for the survival of PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi in achieving its goals effectively and efficiently; besides that, the company must be able to overcome and deal with any problems or obstacles that come from within or outside the company.

[9] state that a business strategy based on the product being marketed must be unique compared to other similar products, and the quality of the product must be good so that this information becomes the main strength of the product in competing in the industry.

B. Strategic Analysis

[10] explain that the business environment can be divided into two, namely: (a) External Environment: General Environment (opportunities and threats) and Industrial Environment (threats and strengths), (b) Internal Environment, including strengths and weaknesses.

C. External Factor Evaluation (EFE) and Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE)

Internal environmental analysis is based on factors in companies that can be controlled [14]. The company's internal processes are then analysed using a functional approach, namely the analysis carried out by all organisational functions by identifying the company's internal aspects [13]. Analysis of the external environment in business development aims to evaluate events and trends beyond the company's control. The internal environment discusses the company's strengths and weaknesses, while the external environment leads to opportunities and threats [3]. So internal factors affect the formation

of strengths and weaknesses, while external factors affect the formation of opportunities and threats [12]. IFE is a form of strategy formulation tool used to summarise and evaluate the strengths and weaknesses in a business and also shows the basis for identifying and evaluating the relationship between these areas. At the same time, EFE is a tool for the company's external factors related to significant opportunities and threats [7].

D. SWOT Analysis

The SWOT matrix is a vital matching tool and can make it easier for companies to develop four types of strategies, including the SO (strength – opportunities) strategy, which is a strategy that is carried out by maximising the strengths it has to maximise the opportunities it has, the ST (strength – threats) strategy is a strategy used by the company to maximise its strengths to deal with threats that arise from outside; the WO (weaknesses - opportunities) strategy is a strategy used by the company to cover the company's weaknesses as much as possible by taking advantage of existing opportunities from external factors, and the WT (weakness – threats) strategy is a strategy to minimise the company's shortcomings or weaknesses and deal with threats that arise from external factors [6].

According to [19], SWOT analysis identifies various factors that systematically formulate company strategy; this analysis is based on the logic that can maximise Strengths and Opportunities but simultaneously minimise Weaknesses and Threats.), research shows that company performance can be determined by a combination of internal and external factors; both factors are considered in the SWOT analysis by comparing the external factors' Opportunities and Threats with internal Strengths and Weaknesses [4].

SWOT analysis aims to analyse and evaluate business processes during the company's strategic planning. Focus on internal and external factors to achieve company goals [33]. SWOT analysis is an activity to see PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi from internal and external aspects. Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) facilitates internal environmental analysis techniques in the SWOT Matrix. External Factor Evaluation (EFE) facilitates external environmental analysis techniques in SWOT. While the analysis of the internal environment will provide an overview of the advantages and disadvantages of PT. Coffee Love Revolver.

TABLE 1: SWOT MATRIX

<i>Internal</i>	Kekuatan (S)	Kelemahan (W)
<i>Eksternal</i>	Daftar Kekuatan	Daftar Kelemahan
Peluang (O)	S-O Strategy	W-O Strategy
Daftar Peluang	Gunakan kekuatan untuk meraih Peluang	Memperkecil Kelemahan dengan memanfaatkan Peluang
Ancaman (T)	S-T Strategy	W-T Strategy
Daftar Ancaman	Gunakan Kekuatan untuk menghindari Ancaman	Memperkecil Kelemahan dan menghindari Ancaman

Source: Hubeis and Najib (2014)

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi or Revolver Cangu, having its address at Jalan Nelayan No.5 Cangu, Bali, using primary data. The method used in analysing the data in this study is by using the qualitative method. The qualitative research method is used to examine the condition of scientific objects, where the researcher is the key

instrument, the data collection technique is done by triangulation (combined), the data analysis is inductive, and the results of qualitative research emphasise meaning rather than generalisation. Objects in qualitative research are natural objects or natural settings, so this research method is often referred to as the naturalistic method [24].

This study uses data collection techniques by interviewing the management of PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi and several of its employees with a list of questions compiled based on SWOT analysis variables. In conducting interviews, researchers need to listen carefully and record what was stated by the informant [24].

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Company Profile

PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi is a company engaged in food and beverage trading. PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi was established on September 12, 2014, by starting a coffee shop in the Seminyak, Badung area called Revolver Espresso. The owner of this coffee shop is Katty Fiona Allan, one of the bartenders from Australia. Until now, PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi already has three coffee shops in Seminyak, Petitenget, and Canggu. With a separate office located at Jalan Beraban, Seminyak.

The vision of PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi is "To Build Iconic Eatery, Cafe and Bar Brand and Memorable Human Experiences in Bali and Beyond. The atmosphere of the shop, which is designed with a unique nuance, namely cowboy-themed, and the taste presented also has a distinctive Revolver coffee with the characteristics of PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi, the price offered is not cheap, so that the visitors to PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi who attended, were mainly from the upper-middle class, and it is undeniable that the Revolver shop is one of the places Indonesian artists visit. To maintain customer loyalty PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi further improves and maintains its best quality in terms of products and services by not implementing price/value reductions to attract lower-class customers.

B. Results of Identification of External Factors (Opportunities and Threats)

Based on the research results at the "Revolver Espresso" coffee shop, external factors, opportunities and threats that affect the business of the "Revolver Espresso" coffee shop were obtained. Several external factors related to the development of this coffee shop, namely:

Opportunity

1. Have the opportunity to expand global operations
2. The development of the coffee drinking lifestyle trend among the community
3. The development of e-commerce technology

Threat

1. The competition in the coffee shop business is getting tougher
2. Increase in raw materials from suppliers
3. The bad effects of coffee can be a problem for society
4. The number of coffee substitute products such as tea, soft drinks, milk, or juice is sold at relatively low prices
5. Government Policy

C. Results of Identification of Internal Factors (Strengths and Weaknesses)

Based on the results of research at the "Revolver Espresso" coffee shop, it is found that the internal factors of strengths and weaknesses that affect the business of the "Revolver Espresso" coffee shop are obtained. Several internal factors related to the development of this coffee shop, namely :

Strengths

1. Quality products and raw materials used
2. Taste quality that is difficult to imitate by competitors
3. Best quality service

4. The products sold vary
5. A unique and comfortable place of business
6. Have potential employees who can be trained easily
7. The outlet is located in an area with perfect economic conditions

Weaknesses

1. The price of the product is relatively high
2. Promotions that are carried out are not optimal
3. Locations that are constrained by vehicle parking spaces
4. other competitors have superior brands
5. Focus more on foreign markets

D. External Environmental Analysis

- 1). Opportunity to expand global operations

PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi has coffee products that can be enjoyed by the world community with more repeat consumers who are foreigners. For this reason, Revolver provides the best quality products and services to increase its market share.

- 2). The growing trend of drinking coffee lifestyle

Lifestyle developments, especially for teenagers, have made Revolver a "hangout" facility and fulfil their social media needs, so Revolver always creates comfortable and unique place conditions.

- 3). The development of e-commerce technology

This technological development requires the business sector to be able to follow trends in increasing sales. This is an essential factor in the era of globalisation because nowadays, everything has been facilitated with digital technology, which makes us have to keep up with technological developments. In increasing its sales, Revolver takes advantage of technological advances by collaborating with Gojek in online sales services.

- 4). Company business competition

One of the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic is being able to make people who have been laid off or laid off build a business, and one of them is the café coffee business so that there are more and more new coffee shops around Revolver, so Revolver further improves the quality and service of its products.

- 5). Economic factors for the increase in raw materials

Tax increases can cause this, or the exchange rate tends to fluctuate, so Revolver can only evaluate the use of coffee beans and look for alternative suppliers.

- 6). The bad effects of coffee can be a problem.

Some people think that the effects of coffee can interfere with their health, such as insomnia and poor caffeine content. What Revolver does is present product variants that do not contain coffee.

- 7). Coffee substitute products

Coffee substitute products that are also in great demand are tea, soft drinks, milk, or juice which are sold at relatively low prices with the number of drink franchises that have mushroomed in Indonesia. Revolver in overcoming this is by adding product variations and maintaining quality.

- 8). Government policy

The policy, especially during the Covid-19 Pandemic, where restrictions on operating hours began to apply to all business sectors, so Revolver chose to increase its online sales.

E. Internal Environmental Analysis

1). Quality products

PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi always prioritises the quality of its products and services to retain customers. Raw materials using the best imported and local products.

2). A taste that is hard to imitate

PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi presents its flagship coffee product with a unique recipe drafted directly by the owner. The owner is a famous former barista in his country (Australia). So for competitors, it will be tough to imitate the distinctive taste of Revolver products.

3). Best quality service

In retaining its customers, PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi in addition to presenting the best products also provides a friendly service, always pays attention to the needs of its customers and is ready to replace losses for poor service.

4). Products vary

In addition to the main product, Kopi Revolver, there are various beverage and food products served. In addition, there is also merchandise in the form of coffee powder or coffee beans in the form of packaging, clothes and accessories for sale.

5). A unique and comfortable place for business

The layout and atmosphere of the restaurant are made so unique, attractive and comfortable, and this was designed directly by the owner. It can attract customers to enjoy their coffee at Revolver.

6). Potential employees who can be trained easily

Revolver employees always receive training to support the quality of Revolver products or services, with the best quality employees, PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi can maintain its quality, so Revolver has training programs for employees, especially the service department.

7). Surrounding economic conditions

The Seminyak and Canggu areas have upper-middle-level tourists, so Revolver outlets are in perfect economic conditions. The field survey results for opening a new branch showed the owner chose the Canggu area with a broader area

8). to open a new branch.

9). High price

Suppose we compare the prices offered by competitors with those presented by PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi is included in the middle to the upper market category for the coffee shop industry in Bali.

9). Promotion is not maximal.

Promotions carried out by Revolver are only through digital and WOM (Word of Mouth) marketing, and very rarely do product promotions.

10). Location constraints

PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi has three places for its efforts. However, the whole place is less strategic, causing a lack of parking space.

11). Competitor

A reasonably tough competitor in the coffee shop industry is Starbucks, where the coffee brand is already well known worldwide and has a superior brand.

12). Focus on the foreign market

The business location is in the tourism zone, PT, with pretty expensive product prices. Revolver Cinta Kopi meets the needs of foreign tourists more than local people, especially the Balinese, who are less familiar with Revolver Espresso.

In running a business, developing a business strategy is an important thing that needs to be done from the start. The business strategy is the effort of PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi in taking policies and guidelines that have commitments and integrated actions and is designed to build excellence in business competition to meet and achieve its business goals, which can be done by improving and maintaining the quality of the products produced (quality control), services that can provide satisfaction to customers with predetermined standards, creating new product variants (product development strategy) which can indirectly attract new customers, and for now the market share at PT. This Cinta Kopi revolver is the upper-middle-class where these people can still enjoy their product variants during the Covid-19 Pandemic, so PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi also requires marketing intelligence to develop and determine market opportunities. The emergence of coffee shops in Indonesia in the last few years does not necessarily make PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi is pessimistic in marketing its products. PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi has consistently put forward its sales strategy yearly. Especially now, PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi has a new challenge in the form of the emergence of the covid-19 pandemic. This means that PT is increasingly intensifying the maximisation of digital social media. Revolver Cinta Kopi to meet sales targets. With the business strategy, PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi can determine the company's direction by identifying it in terms of markets, competitors, customers and so on so that during this Covid-19 Pandemic, PT. Revolver can open new branches.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results at the "Revolver Espresso" coffee shop, external factors, opportunities and threats that affect the business of the "Revolver Espresso" coffee shop were obtained. From what can be seen that the coffee shop business is currently up-and-coming for the long term because there are many enthusiasts for this type of business. This concludes that the strategy implemented can provide good results for the company to develop widely. While the results of the research for internal factors, strengths and weaknesses indicate that the quality of the Revolver Espresso business is very high, starting from the services provided, the uniqueness of the place of business to the food, snacks, and the main thing is the drink, namely coffee. Alternative strategy options that can be applied to PT. Revolver Cinta Kopi is to improve and maintain the quality of the products produced (quality control), services that can provide satisfaction to customers with predetermined standards, create new product variants (product development strategy) that can indirectly attract new customers, and marketing intelligence to be able to develop and determine market opportunities.

This article can be a study for future researchers and should be able to develop this research more broadly. Future research is expected to use the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) to evaluate the strategy objectively based on the critical success factors (internal and external) that have been identified.

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